

TOWARDS PRINCIPLES AND OBJECTIVES OF ISLAMIC ECONOMIC ORGANIZATION

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Abstract

Islamic Economic is an old concept but a very young discipline in the academic sciences. It lacks the required extent and level of theories and models needed for expansion and implementation of the framework provided by Islam. In these circumstances, unawareness and confusion exist as to the form of the Islamic Economic system and instruments.

The main difference between the present economic system and the Islamic economic system is that the later is based on keeping in view certain social objectives for the benefit of human beings and society. Islam, through its various principles, guides human life and ensures free enterprise and trade. That is the reason why the conventional banker does not have to be concerned with the moral implications of the business venture for which money is lent.

Key Words: Islamic Economy, Quran, Zakat, Nafs,

Introduction

There exists a vast array of literature on Islamic economics. The library of the Kiel Institute of World Economics counts more than 80 titles on this topic. There are numerous websites dealing with Islamic economics. Even a Journal, "Review of Islamic Economics" was edited to underscore the importance of this topic. Looking at this literature it is not easy to define what the subject-matter of Islamic economics is. Phillip (1990, p. 126) maintains that "The point of departure" of the theory of Islamic economics "is not the investigation of the actual economic behavior in an existing Moslem society or the historical evidence for such a behavior in the past. Rather the Muslim economist treats an ideal order projected into the past as a historical fact and then draws from their legitimization for his own theoretical endeavors". These economists are chiefly occupied with the criticism of western concepts of economics, capitalism and communism and with the presenting of a moral view of Islamic economy including Islamic Socialism. We can therefore distinguish between two different branches of Islamic economics, one analytical and the other one based on moral values. The analytical branch uses the methodology of mainstream Economics to find solutions for problems understood as Islamic economic problems. Examples are "The Concept of Zakah Evasion: An economic Interpretation" (Diabi 1993), "Measuring Consumption Function in an Islamic Framework" (Bendjilali; al-Zamil 1993) or "A Comprehensive Macroeconomic Income Determination Model for an Islamic Economy" (Hussain 1994). One important sub-branch of this literature identifies an Islamic economy with an interest-free economy and analyses the question how such an economy would function theoretically and in practice (Mills, Presley 1999; Dalkusu 1999). In the following we discuss first the issue of the ban on interest and afterwards the concept of Islamic economics based on moral values. In contrast to the conventional economic analysis we subsequently discuss the functioning of an Islamic economy. A summary of the conclusions is given in the last part of the paper.

Islamic Economics and Moral Values the branch of Islamic economics based on moral values is analytically less rigorous. Quran (1997, p. 1) writes that "The declared purpose of Islamic economics is to identify and establish an

economic order that confirms to Islamic scripture and traditions". According to world Dictionary & Encyclopedia (01.06.04) Islamic Economics is economics in the political context of Islam that respects its associated ethical codes. These definitions concentrate on religious morality and its corresponding institutional foundations in society (zakat, ethical investment etc.) as the quintessence of Islamic economics. It is not easy to understand this kind of conceptualization of an Islamic economics. Economics is a science, meaning that it formulates laws of how an economy works. Islamic economics therefore, should study economic laws according to which a society in which Moslems live would develop economically. If these Moslems live according to the scripture and its ethical codes, will there exist laws different from those Studied in the conventional economic analysis describing the functioning of a modern economy? In this case Islamic economics should scrutinize these laws. But in case the same laws as in a modern economy apply but there are differences in the economic order, where for example special care is taken for the poor or some investments are forbidden due to their unethical character and others are urged due to their moral value, there is no basis for an Islamic economics but only for a different economic order under the influence of Islam. As a matter of fact, there may be differences between a market economy shaped by the behavior of individuals not knowing any limitation in their moral attitude and another one shaped by the behavior of Moslems, who live according to ethical codes mentioned in the literature. But it is not easily possible to draw the conclusion that such differences can lay the foundation for a new economic science called Islamic economics. No meaningful economic analysis can be based on a long code of moral conduct consisting of many moral sentences. We propose to characterize a Moslem economy as one populated by individuals who control their Nafs. This would make a real difference in the functioning of the economy comparing to a society where this is not the case. To understand this significant difference one has to know what is meant by the Islamic⁵ concept "Nafs". A simple definition would be to describe Nafs as that entity in the human being, which has forgotten God and seeks the fulfillment of its being solely in the pleasures of this earthen life. Curious enough, most of the elementary economics text books begin with a statement which makes Economics a science of scrutinizing the laws of functioning of an economy in which individuals with eager Nafs live. For Nafs, its earthen wants are unlimited. This seems to be the fundamental statement at the beginning of the conventional economics science. Some citations from text books may underline this claim: "Economics is the study of how people, individually and collectively allocate their limited resources to try to satisfy their unlimited wants" (Byrns; Stone 1995, p. 5)

"Human wants are virtually unlimited, whereas the resources available to satisfy these wants are limited" (Sloman 2000, p. 2). "Moreover, it is realistic to assume that the utility perception of a human being changes with the development of the economy in a manner that the more they have the more they want (free translation, Schumann et al. 1999, p. 6)

"To economics means to reduce as far as possible the trade-off between unlimited wants and the limited resources which are available for their satisfaction" (Bontrup 1998, p. 29)

A Moslem, who controls his Nafs has limited wants and the resources to fulfill these limited wants are provided by the divine promise. As it is said in the verse 11:6:

"There is no moving creature on earth but its sustenance dependent on God: He knoweth the time and place of its definite abode and its temporary deposit: All is in a clear Record" (Yusuf Ali) A Moslem is not therefore disturbed about his living means and to economize for him means to search for the proper employment to become vested with the promised means. This is a fundamental difference from the usual conceptualization of the economic activity as expressed in the above citations. A human being with unlimited wants is eager because he knows no limitation and wishes to have always more in spite of the limited resources. Everytime one of his wants is fulfilled, others will unfold and he is permanently under pressure to fulfil the new ones. The very moment he gets satisfaction he develops the feeling of scarcity and shortage. He is therefore permanently discontented. In this process he is constantly⁶ occupied with the question of how to mobilize the limited resources to fulfill ever newly unfolding wants. He is never in a position of stillness. He is disturbed. In contrast to such a human being a Moslem with clear

and limited wants is modest, content and undisturbed. His wants are limited because he is aware of the fact that he is on this planet to diminish his sanctionable failures by divine order and he is availed with enough resources to fulfill these limited wants.

What is Islamic Economy?

A. Islamic Economy Islam is a comprehensive way of life, which strikes the balance between the spiritual and the material need of human being. One of the important aspects in human life is the need for a comprehensive system in order to govern their life and to ensure all the needs are catered adequately including the material needs such as the financial management. This aspect of life is closely related to the fast growing industry in the world nowadays, which is the Islamic financial services industry. An Islamic economy is a market economy guided by moral values. Economic activities are based on principles of cooperation and responsibility. Cooperation means that an economic exchange shall be beneficial to both parties involved. Transactions in which one party wins at the expense of the other are not permissible in Islam. Thus, monopolistic dealings, usury, and exploitation are prohibited. Principles of Islamic Economy

Transactions that allow both parties to win are permissible, and these include most types of activities needed for economic prosperity. Performance-based arrangements, like profit sharing or partnership, represent the most cooperative form of beneficial Agreements, and thus are highly encouraged in Islam. Responsibility means that each individual is entitled for reward or return based on his effort and contribution. Thus gambling and lotteries are not permissible. Gambling allows an individual to gain based on pure luck, not on merit or effort. It shifts wealth blindly among participants leading to improper distribution of wealth. Gambling is a clear form of a zero-sum game where one party wins only if the other loses, and thus causes hatred and enmity among

Participants. A society where lotteries or gambling like activities prevail is a zero-sum society, where the winner takes all, and the rest is doomed to fail. B. Islamic Economics

Islamic economics is a framework for studying economic activities that allow mutual benefit of exchange to be realized. It provides proper tools and techniques for evaluating economic decisions, showing when and how to achieve win/win outcomes and avoid Win/lose or lose/lose ones. Islamic economics is based on the principle that Allah the Almighty created this world with plenty of resources that satisfy the needs of everyone. Thus one person's success is not necessarily achieved at the expense or exclusion of the success of others. This "win/win" framework leads to better economic behavior and performance, and thus promises better future for mankind. Islamic Banks are financial institutions established according to principles of Islamic Economics. They provide finance and financial services in a manner leading to mutual benefit. Although finance activities are deeply rooted in Islamic history, formal Islamic banking is a recent phenomenon, whereby the first Islamic bank was established around 1963.

Sources of Shari'a law Shari'a law is derived from a number of primary and secondary Sources.

a) The Quran is a primary source of law and is believed by Muslims to Contain the word of God as revealed to the Prophet Mohammed. Evidence found in other sources of Shari'a law is subject to the Qur'an.

b) Sunnah Sunnah literally means "well known path". The sunnah is a primary source of law and comprises traditional accounts of what the Prophet Mohammed said or did during his life which have legal content. Sunnah also comprises the sayings of others tacitly approved by the Prophet's silence.

c) Hadith A further primary source of law is the narrative record of sayings and actions of the Prophet Mohammed known as hadith (plural ahadith). The extent to which sunnah is derived or differentiated from ahadith depends on

the context and school of thought being considered. d) Qiyas represents the process of reasoning whereby the principles found in the Qur'an and sunnah are extended to new cases by analogy.

e) Ijma represents the consensus of the Islamic community (whether at a local or global academic level) on a particular issue.

(f) Ijtihad Ijtihad is the interpretation and the opinion of Islamic jurists on a particular issue. Qiyas, ijma and ijtihad are all secondary sources of Shari'a law. 3. Issues relating to interpretation and application of Shari'a law Since Shari'a law is not a single codified body of law and is open to interpretation, the opinions of Shari'a scholars may differ on the same question of Shari'a law depending on the school of thought to which particular scholars belong. In addition, scholars' views on Questions of Shari'a law may change over time. This can lead to uncertainty and inconsistency of interpretation and application of Shari'a law across the Islamic world.

Lastly, it is said that it is possible to reduce poverty by following Islamic economic system because it take care of society and social justice , which is ignored by western economy. It is the system, that says: "He who sleeps on a full stomach whilst his neighbor goes hungry is not one of us." (Saying of Prophet Muhammad PBUH)

"Allah will deprive usury of all blessing, but will give increase for deeds of charity"

[Surah-Baqarah (2): 276] "If the debtor is in a difficulty, grant him time till it is easy for him to repay. But if ye remit it by way of charity, that is best for you if ye only knew."

[Surah-Baqarah (2): 280] The Role of Money The traditional definition of the time value of money leads one to assume that profit maximization is the objective of investors irrespective of whether or not the earning of profit has made someone else worse off. Some economists have termed the maximization of profit as the sole objective of corporations. This view cannot be supported or defended since the profit maximization process may lead to perverse outcomes. When financial operations are removed of moralistic tone, competitive markets fail to achieve the efficient allocation of a country's resources. In Islam money in itself is not considered, as actual capital only exists when money, along with other resources, is sunk into productive activities. Linking the use of money to productive purposes invariably brings into action the factor of labor, a process from which benefits pass on to society.

Benefits of Islamic Economy

Given the constraints of time and resources, this study could not fully exploit all the issues under this topic. The researcher therefore recommends that further studies be conducted in the following areas. 1. The effects of modularization of banking systems components in the adoption of technology in the Islamic banking. 2. The potential of Islamic banking in the non-Islamic countries.

In some countries such as Pakistan, Iran and Sudan all banks are operating according to Islamic financial law but in some other countries such as Bangladesh, Egypt, Indonesia, Jordan and Malaysia Islamic banking services are provided through conventional banking. There is big movement started in the Western countries especially United Kingdom, Australia and United State (Shanmugam, Perumal and Ridzwa, 2004)

The Problem

According to the figures of Office for National Statistics 2001, there was 1.6 million (2.8%) Muslims living in the United Kingdom (www.news.bbc.co.uk), but according to Home Secretary the Muslim population is increasing with

high growth rate. In just seven years there is an increase of 40,000 Muslims in the UK and figures reached on 2 million which consist of 3.3% of total UK population (www.guardian.co.uk).

Office for National Statistics 2001 figures UK there are about 1.6 million Muslims are living in UK, which comprises 2.8% of the total population of the country, in which 50% are estimated to reside in the London area (www.news.bbc.co.uk). According to Home Secretary UK, Jacqui Smith, in United Kingdom the Muslim population is nearly 2 millions. It means that the Muslim population is about 3.3% of the UK population (www.guardian.co.uk).
 Islamic Banking in the UK: Opportunities and Challenges Page 20

Figure: 1

The Muslim population in some European countries Country	Total Population	Muslim Population	Percentage%
Belgium 1	10.3 million	0.4 million	4%
Denmark 2	5.4 million	279,000	5%
France 3	62.3 million	5 to 6 million	8 to 9.6%
Germany 4	82.5 million	3 million	3.6%
Italy 5	58.4 million	825,000	1.4%
Netherland 6	16.3 million	945,000	5.8%
Spain 7	43.1 million	1 million	2.3%
Sweden 8	9.0 million	300,000	3%
Switzerland 9	7.4 million	310,800	4.2%
United Kingdom 10	58.8 million	1.6 million	2.8%
United Kingdom *11	2.0 million (in 2008)	3.3%	

Research Methodology

This research will be based on real-practices information available in the financial market; in relevant to Islamic financial institutions within the Middle East financial markets.

Primary Research

Primary research will be performed based on: Research and questionnaire with industry experts. Research and questionnaire with technology experts.

Secondary Research

Secondary research will be performed on the basis of Data available within the Islamic and conventional financial institutions' annual reports, websites and marketing materials. Data available through international organizations and big four annual industry review reports.

This study also recommends that the Islamic banks should sensitize their customers on the importance of technology in banking. While the experts appreciate the need for technology in Islamic banking, this need is not well-appreciated among the customers. By having the customers appreciate the technology, the Islamic banks may find it much easier to implement such technology and fully exploit them to attain such levels of developments witnessed in the conventional banking sector.

Conclusions

A religion can promote the development of sciences but it is not for the purpose of founding different branches of sciences. We could not find any foundation for an Islamic economics as a science based on the ban of interest. Also an Islamic economics based on the idea of zakah and ethical investment is too far away to have a general validity characterizing a science. But there may be crucial differences between a market economy shaped by the behavior of individuals not knowing any limitation in their moral attitude and another one shaped by the behavior of Moslems who are obliged, according to the religious rule, to control their Nafs. In a Moslem economy inflation and unemployment are rare phenomena and as a rule the growth rate is moderate. The economy lives in peace with nature and the individuals are content, undisturbed and enjoying their lives. Poverty, of course, exists. But this poverty is accepted as one of the means to diminish sanctionable failures for those individuals who have been transgressive in their past lives. But there exists also the principle of charity where the poor are taken care of and a basic solidarity exists where the feeling of brotherhood prevails Section II. Concept of Economic Development and Inclusion in Islam is considered a rule-based system which specifies rules for social and economic activities of the society. In this respect, economic principles of Islam deal with (a) the rules of behavior (similar to the concept of economic institutions) as they relate to resource allocation, production, exchange, distribution and redistribution; (b) economic implications of the operations of these rules; and (c) incentive structure and policy recommendations for achieving rules compliance that would allow convergence of the actual economy to the ideal economic system envisioned by Islam.

References

- Asmani, A. (2006). Banks Get Light to Offer Another Islamic Product. The Straits Times (Singapore), 13 June 2006.
- Bendjilali, Boualem; al-Zamil, Yousif A. (1993) .Measuring Consumption Function in an Islamic Framework, in: Review of Islamic Economics, Vol. 2, p. 34.
- Bontrup, Heinz-J. (1998). Volkswirtschaftslehre, R. Oldenbourg Verlag, Munich, Vienna.
- Byrns, Ralph T.; Stone, Gerald W. (1995). Economics, Sixth Edition, Harper Collins, New York.
- Dalkusu, Ibrahim N. (1999). Grundlagen des zinslosen Wirtschaftens, Eigentum, Geld, Riba und Unternehmungsformen nach den Lehren des Islam, Dissertation, Dike Verlag AG, St Gallen/Lachen SZ .
- David C. F. (2011). Global Security Studies: The Hawaala System. Diplomacy Department, Norwich: Norwich University. (International Turnkey Systems (ITS) Group, 2013) .

Diabi, Ali (1993).The Concept of Zakah Evasion: An Economic Interpretation, in: Review of Islamic Economics, Vol. 2, pp. 17-28.

Hussain, Muhammad (1994).A Comprehensive Macroeconomic Income Distribution Model for an Islamic Economy, in: The Pakistan Development Review, 33: 4 Part, pp. 1301-1314.

Imady, O. and Seibel H. D. (2006), Principles and Products of Islamic Finance, Working Paper No. 2006-1, Development Research Center, University of Cologne, Germany.

Islamic Finance News (2012May, 16th). Procuring banking systems and technology in the Islamic banking sector. Islamic Finance News.

Jamwal, N.S. (2002). Hawaala – The Invisible Financing System of Terrorism. Strategic Analysis: IDSA.

Justin, C., Brian M., Alice M. & Anthony P. (2012). Procuring banking Systems and Technology in the Islamic Banking Sector. Islamic Finance News.

Kabir, M. H. & Mervyn K. L. (2007.) Handbook of Islamic Banking, p2.

Kuran, Timur (1997).The Genesis of Islamic Economics: A Chapter in the Politics of Moslem Identity, in: Social Research, Vol. 64, No. 2 (Summer 1997), pp. 1-22.

Mills, Paul S.; Presly, John R. (1999).Islamic Finance: Theory and Practice, Macmillan Press LTD, Basingstoke .

Mugenda, O.M & Mugenda, A.G. (1999). Research methods Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches. Nairobi: East African Educational Publishers.

Opie, C. (2004). Doing Educational Research: A Guide for First Time Researchers. New York: Apprentice Hall.

Peil, M. (1995). Social Research Methods: A Handbook for Africa. Nairobi: East Africa Educational Publishers.

Petersen, D. J. (1995). Monetary Aggregates, Payments Technology, and Institutional Factors. Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta Economic Review, 8, p.30.

Phillip, Thomas (1990).The Idea Of Islamic Economics, in: Die Welt des Islams XXX, pp. 117-139.

Uma, S. (2003). Research methods for Business 4th edition: A Skill Building Approach

Venardos, A. M. (2006), Islamic Banking and Finance in South-east Asia: Its Developments and Future, Asia-Pacific Business Series Vol. 3 (2nd ed.).

Wilson, R. (1999). Challenges and Opportunities for Islamic Banking and Finance in the West: The UK Experience. Islamic Economic Studies, Vol. 7, Nos. 1&2.

Yee, L. (2006). OCBC Scores on 5-year Risk-adjusted Returns. The Business Times (Singapore), 9 February 2006.

Zamir, I. (1997). Finance and Development. Islamic Financial Systems, p.45.

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Quran-translation according to Yusuf Ali.

(<http://www.compsoc.man.ac.uk/~moiz/quran/browse.cgi?sura=>)

Schumann, Jochen; Meyer, Ulrich; Ströbele, Wolfgang (1999)

Grundzüge der mikroökonomischen Theory, 7th edition, Springer, Berlin

Slooman, John (2000). Economics, Fourth Edition, Prentice Hall, London, New York

Word iQ Dictionary & Encyclopedia Islamic economics, http://www.wordiq.com/definition/Islamic_economics